

LINGUISTIC, CULTURAL CONCEPT OF RUSSIAN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND ITS IMPORTANCE

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Annotation: *The article presents the main parts of the linguocultural concept of teaching Russian in a polyethnic environment. The further development of the project will be based on the study of the processes that take place in education on the basis of the concept of linguoculture.*

Keywords: *linguoculturology, multilingual language person, phenomenon, non-equivalent vocabulary, background vocabulary.*

The linguoculturological concept of teaching the Russian language, which is being developed in the republic, is based on the general psychological and pedagogical, linguodidactic and linguistic foundations of language teaching, at the same time it assumes linguocultural and logical foundations and is based on the basic concepts of the science of linguoculturology. Let us briefly characterize linguoculturology as a new branch of linguistic science and its basic concepts.

Cultural linguistics is a scientific discipline that borders between the sciences that study culture and philology (linguistics).

The subject of the study of linguoculturology is the material and spiritual culture created by mankind and expressed in the language.

Linguoculturology studies the national-structural semantics of language units in order to understand them in their entirety of content and shades, to a degree as close as possible to their perception by native speakers of a given language and culture. With this approach, linguoculturology is an aspect of linguistics that studies the problem of reflecting national culture in language and the problem of speech activity in the context of intercultural communication.

The focus of linguoculturology is a person, considered as a carrier of language and culture.

From the foregoing, we can conclude that the main objects of study of linguoculturology are "Man", "Language", "Culture" in their relationship.

In the triad of these initial concepts, the first place is occupied by the concept of "Man" and the concept of "linguistic personality" arising from it.

A linguistic personality is a personality expressed in language, that is, in the oral and written texts it creates, which ensure its vital activity in society.

A multilingual language person is a person who speaks several languages.

The relationship of language and culture is one of the basic concepts of the linguoculturological concept of language teaching. This issue can be considered in three aspects:

1. Language as an indicator of the general culture of a person, his speech culture and culture of communication.

2. Language as a phenomenon of culture and as a treasury of the culture of the people, its custodian and means of transmission from one generation to another.

3. Language in its aesthetic function as a means of creating literature, one of the most important components of culture.

The concept is, as it were, a clot of culture in the mind of a person, something in the form of which culture enters the inner world of a person. And, on the other hand, a concept is something by which a person himself enters the culture, and in some cases influences it. The concept is the main cell of culture in the mental world of a person (Yu. S. Stepanov).

The conceptosphere is a national linguistic picture of the world, expressed with the help of concepts and their names - words.

The keywords-concepts of the Russian language include such words as distance, road, steppe, field, forest, river, etc., which is associated with the landscape of Russia. Key words of the language form the basis of artistic images. The road, the path - the favorite motif of S. Yesenin's poems; dawn, dawn - a hymn of admiration for nature.

In the work of M. Karim, such concepts as life, road, path, path, time, person, happiness can be identified as key; from the concrete world of his environment: earth, birds, flowers, 'from the world of human feelings: love, heart. These words testify to the life-affirming, optimistic position of the poet.

Awareness of language as a phenomenon of culture, as a cultural and historical environment that contributes to the storage and transmission of the material and spiritual culture of society from generation to generation, leads to the need to describe language units from the point of view of the national cultural component of meaning. First of all, this applies to vocabulary, phraseology and aphorism. The formation of the ethnolinguoculturological competence of students on the basis of this

material is the most important part of teaching Russian and native languages. According to the degree of cultural coloring, vocabulary is distinguished 1) non-equivalent (realities); 2) background; 3) connotative.

Non-equivalent vocabulary - words denoting the realities of Russian culture. Realia - words (and phrases) that name objects characteristic of the life (everyday life, culture, social and historical development) of one people and alien to another. For example, round dance, ditty, Russian (dancing), balalaika, Palekh miniature; accordion, kalach, kvass, pie, porridge, etc.

Background vocabulary is words whose meaning is the same in different languages, but the real content is different, since in different cultures words have their own content of extralinguistic knowledge, their own lexical background: cinema, school, theater, etc.

The lexical background is everything that stands behind the given word in reality. The lexical background is steadily known to all members of the national-cultural and linguistic community of people.

Connotative vocabulary (kon-so; notation - meaning, that is - meaning) - vocabulary that, in addition to lexical meaning, has various kinds of emotionally expressive, metaphorical, symbolic meanings, for example, oak is a symbol of a strong person, and also not very intelligent; snake - the meaning of cunning, deceit; hare - cowardice, timidity, etc.

Of great interest to students are written works describing concepts: water, earth, sun, light-darkness, good-evil, beauty, truth, happiness, soul, heart, friend and many others. These works usually consist of five parts. 1. My associations with the word (the word in my mind) (for example, the word moon caused associations: full, night, stars, month, full moon, winter, frost, cold, wolf, etc.). 2. Associations with a word in a group of people up to 20 people (conditionally: the word is in the minds of the people). 3. Dictionary portrait of the word (the word in all dictionaries available to students: explanatory, etymological, phraseological, word-formation, compatibility dictionaries, synonyms, antonyms). 4. The word in the wisdom of the people (proverbs, sayings with the word). 5. Text portrait of the word (aphorisms with the word, lines from songs, poems and prose). Such work gives students an idea of the richness and versatility of a single word, of the life of a word in the culture of the people and of the reflection of the culture and self-consciousness of the people in every word.

A great place in the cultural concept of teaching the Russian language is given to phraseology, aphorism and text.

Phraseologism is a stable combination of words, the features of which are stability, reproducibility in finished form, non-derivation of a holistic

meaning from the meanings of the constituent words, idiomaticity - untranslatability into other languages.

The character, way of life, customs and traditions of the Russian people are reflected in Russian proverbs and sayings.

A proverb is a figurative folk expression that has entered into everyday speech, containing a complete thought, for example, Good brotherhood is better than wealth. Being a guest is good, but being at home is better. Business - time, fun - an hour.

A proverb, unlike a proverb, does not contain a complete judgment: it is only a part of it (seven Fridays in a week, put your teeth on a shelf, bet).

Aphorisms are winged words, that is, brief quotations from literature, sayings of historical figures, scientists, philosophers that have entered our speech. For example, aphorisms from the works of A. S. Pushkin: All ages are submissive to love, 'his example to others is science; From the ship to the ball, 'What is the coming day preparing for me? and etc.

Language is a way of existence and transmission of culture, the implementation of which occurs through texts. The text is the main unit of the formation of a linguistic personality, since it is through the text that the student gets the opportunity to acquire new knowledge and values, the spiritual culture of his own and other people, to compare their moral and aesthetic positions.

Mastering the norms of speech communication, developing communicative competence is one of the goals of language teaching at school, to achieve which it is necessary to describe the national and cultural characteristics of speech behavior, the rules of intercultural communication.

- Thus, the linguoculturological concept of teaching the Russian language involves: the interconnected study of language and culture;
- education in students of a general humanitarian culture, interest in the spiritual values of their native, including Russian culture;
- fostering tolerance, respect for the language and culture of other peoples, understanding of universal human values as reflected in national cultures;
- the formation of a language culture among students as an indicator of the general culture of a person is a necessary condition for his life and success.

REFERENCES:

1.Sayakhova L.G. Methodology and methodological system for the formation of linguoculturological competence of Turkic-speaking students in

the lessons of the Russian language: Monograph. - Ufa: RIC BashGU, 2010. - 292 p.

2.Vorobyov V.V., Sayakhova L.G. Russian language in the dialogue of cultures: Textbook / Elective course for grades 10-11. — M.: Ladomir, 2006. — 283 p.

4.The culture of the Turkic peoples in the lessons of the Russian language: A guide for the teacher / Compiled by L.G. Sayakhova. - St. Petersburg: Education, 2008. - 163 p.

5.Vasiliev L.M. General problems of linguistics. Theory and methods. - Ufa: RIC BashGU, 2007.

6. Minamatov, Y. E. U. (2021). APPLICATION OF MODULAR TEACHING TECHNOLOGY IN TECHNOLOGY. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 911-913.

7. Minamatov, Y. E. O. G. L., & Nasirdinova, M. H. Q. (2022). APPLICATION OF ICT IN EDUCATION AND TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 738-740.